

Spectral and magnetic studies of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) metal with bidentate Schiff base ligands

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Abstract : The divalent metal complexes of cobalt, nickel and palladium have been prepared with bidentate Schiff bases derived by condensing 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde with 4-hydroxybenzhydrazide. The complexes obtained were characterized on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic moment, conductance, IR, electronic, ^1H NMR as well as thermal analysis. The cobalt and nickel complexes are paramagnetic exhibiting tetrahedral geometry whereas palladium complexes are diamagnetic showing square planar geometry. The IR spectral data revealed that both the Schiff bases behave as bidentate ligands and are coordinated to Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} via azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. X-Ray powder diffraction studies suggest orthorhombic crystal system for all the metal complexes.

Keywords : Schiff base, 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzhydrazide, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} complexes.

Introduction

The literature survey reveals that Schiff base ligand is an excellent coordination ligand and can exhibit variety in the structure of their metal complexes. Some work has been reported on the transition metal complexes of hydrazides^{1,2}. Metal complexes of O, N chelating ligands have attracted considerable attention because of their interesting physico-chemical properties and pronounced biological activities³. Schiff bases and their transition metal complexes have been used as anticancer, antitubercular, antibacterial, antifungal, hypertensive and hypothermic reagents⁴⁻⁶. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to synthesize Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of ligands derived from 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde with 4-hydroxybenzhydrazide and to investigate their crystal structures. The metal complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Vis, ^1H NMR, thermal, magnetic susceptibility and X-ray powder diffraction method.

Results and discussion

All the metal complexes prepared with Schiff bases derived from 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde with 4-hydroxybenzhydrazide are stable

in air and decompose at higher temperature. The physical data are given in Table 1 and are in good agreement with the actual composition. The infrared spectral data of the ligands and their complexes are given in Table 2 and the electronic spectral data of the metal complexes are reported in Table 3. All the complexes are crystalline solids with the colour ranging from yellow to brown. They were insoluble in water but soluble in DMF, DMSO. The molar conductivities of 1×10^{-3} S $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ solutions of the various complexes in DMSO (Table 2) indicate that the complexes behave as non-electrolytes¹⁰.

The infrared spectra of the free ligands were compared with those of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes to determine the bonding mode of the ligands to the metal in the complexes. The free ligands showed a strong absorption in the range $1682\text{--}1685 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ ¹¹. This band appeared in the same region in the spectra of the metal complexes suggesting non involvement of the carbonyl group in coordination to the metal atom. The coordination of azomethine nitrogen is confirmed by the presence of bands at 1646 cm^{-1} in L_1 and 1617 cm^{-1} in L_2 which underwent a shift to a lower frequency after complexation due to the lowering of the electron density upon coordination¹². The phenolic oxygen, after

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the ligand and metal complexes

Ligand/ Complex	Mol. Wt. (Colour)	M.p. (°C)	Stoichiometry	Elemental analysis (%) :				
				Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	M	Cl
C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂	256.00	260	-	64.94	4.63	11.09	-	-
L ₁	(White)			(65.62)	(4.68)	(10.93)		
Co(C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄).H ₂ O	586.93	227	1 : 2	57.60	4.75	9.93	10.36	-
Co(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	(Brown)			(57.24)	(4.08)	(9.54)	(10.04)	
Ni(C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄).H ₂ O	586.69	281	1 : 2	57.90	4.03	9.72	9.65	-
Ni(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	(Yellow)			(57.27)	(4.09)	(9.54)	(10.00)	
Pd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂).Cl.H ₂ O	414.92	244	1 : 1	40.48	3.13	6.74	25.30	8.27
Pd(L ₁).Cl.H ₂ O	(Dark brown)			(39.42)	(3.05)	(7.23)	(25.64)	(8.55)
C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ .Cl	290.50	290	-	57.45	3.85	9.73	-	11.92
L ₂	(White)			(57.83)	(3.78)	(9.69)		(12.22)
Co(C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄ .Cl) ₂ .H ₂ O	655.93	> 320	1 : 2	56.50	3.40	7.85	8.63	10.62
Co(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	(Brown)			(51.22)	(3.35)	(8.53)	(8.98)	(10.82)
Ni(C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄ .Cl) ₂ .H ₂ O	655.69	> 320	1 : 2	50.82	3.49	8.62	8.38	11.05
Ni(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	(Green)			(51.24)	(3.35)	(8.54)	(8.95)	(10.83)
Pd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ .Cl).Cl.H ₂ O	449.42	275	1 : 1	36.28	2.92	6.15	23.49	15.27
Pd(L ₂).Cl.H ₂ O	(Yellow)			(37.38)	(2.22)	(6.23)	(23.67)	(15.79)

Table 2. Infrared spectral, molar conductivity and magnetic susceptibility data of Schiff base and metal complexes

Compd./ Ligand	IR spectral data (cm ⁻¹)					Molar cond. (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
	ν _{C-O}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}	ν _{M-N}	ν _{M-O}		
L ₁	1337	1685	1646	-	-	2.84	-
L ₂	1341	1682	1617	-	-	5.74	-
Co(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	1310	1682	1627	550	464	24.3	4.54
Ni(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	1310	1686	1614	549	463	4.12	3.82
Pd(L ₁).Cl.H ₂ O	1292	1685	1595	551	458	6.20	Diamag.
Co(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	1322	1682	1607	538	471	16.6	4.58
Ni(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	1307	1682	1602	550	424	25.7	3.73
Pd(L ₂).Cl.H ₂ O	1278	1683	1597	552	433	11.6	Diamag.

the loss of O-H proton gets coordinated to the metal. This is supported by shift in the stretching frequency of ν_{C-O} to lower wave numbers by 20–35 cm⁻¹ from its position in the free ligands¹³. In addition, all complexes showed additional weak to medium intensity bands in the region 538–552 and 424–471 cm⁻¹ which were absent in the spectra of ligands, these can be attributed to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} respectively^{14,15}. Thus IR spectra give clear evidence that bonding of the ligand to the metal ion occurs through nitrogen and oxygen in bidentate manner.

The magnetic moments of the complexes were measured at room temperature by Gouy's method using

Hg[Co(SCN)₄] (χ_g = 16.44 × 10⁻⁶ g cm⁻³) as a standard¹⁶. The data is represented in Table 2.

The electronic absorption spectra for these complexes are summarized in Table 3. Electronic spectra of ligands showed three high intensity bands at 30211, 32573, 36101 cm⁻¹ for L₁ and 27932, 30303, 36101 cm⁻¹ for L₂ and are assigned to n → π*, π → π*, σ → σ* transitions respectively. The cobalt(II) complexes are brown and reddish brown in colour for L₁ and L₂. The spectra of Co(L₁)₂.H₂O complexes exhibit bands at 27470, 31750, 32680 cm⁻¹ and Co(L₂)₂.H₂O complexes exhibit bands at 23360, 24510 and 35910 cm⁻¹. The band appearing at

Table 3. UV-Vis and ^1H NMR spectral data of ligand and metal complexes

Compd./ Ligand	Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1})			^1H NMR				
	$(\epsilon = \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-4})$			Chemical shift (δ ppm)				
	Assignments for $d-d$ transition			Aromatic	CH=N	N-H	OH (aldehyde)	OH (amine)
L_1	30211 (1.9)	32573 (2.6)	36101 (1.3)	6.78-7.80	8.32	9.61	11.57	10.12
L_2	27932 (4.1)	30303 (4.8)	36101 (3.7)	6.84-7.83	8.56	10.17	11.99	11.39
$\text{Co}(L_1)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	27470 (3.5)	32680 (4.9)	31750 (4.4)	6.89-7.95	8.42	9.62	-	10.14
$\text{Ni}(L_1)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	28330 (2.2)	32570 (3.9)	34010 (3.5)	6.84-7.78	8.77	9.62	-	10.12
$\text{Pd}(L_1) \cdot \text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	22600 (0.3)	28500 (0.3)	30300 (0.1)	6.29-7.90	8.64	9.64	-	10.11
$\text{Co}(L_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	23360 (4.3)	24510 (4.0)	35910 (3.5)	6.71-7.69	8.69	10.10	-	11.41
$\text{Ni}(L_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	23810 (4.1)	29540 (4.4)	32790 (3.9)	6.87-7.85	8.66	10.11	-	11.40
$\text{Pd}(L_2) \cdot \text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	23419 (1.3)	27777 (1.2)	29411 (1.2)	6.32-7.88	8.77	10.09	-	11.38

23360 and 27470 cm^{-1} in $\text{Co}(L_1)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(L_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ can be assigned to $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1 (P)$ i.e. $d-d$ transition¹⁷ which is characteristic of tetrahedral geometry. The bands appearing at 32680 and 35910 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer transition as observed in most of the tetrahedral complexes¹⁷. This is further supported by magnetic moment values found to be 4.54 and 4.58 B.M. for $\text{Co}(L_1)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(L_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. The magnetic moments of the cobalt(II) complexes of the ligands at room temperature fall in the 4.2-4.8 B.M. range which is characteristic for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹⁶.

The Ni^{II} complexes of ligands L_1 and L_2 exhibit magnetic moments of 3.82 and 3.73 B.M. respectively. Figgis¹⁸ has reported the Ni^{II} complexes with magnetic moments in such range as tetrahedral complex. These Ni^{II} complexes are yellow and green in colour. The absorption spectrum of $\text{Ni}L_1$ complex shows an absorption band at 28330, 32570, 34010 cm^{-1} while $\text{Ni}L_2$ complex shows an absorption band at 23810, 29540 and 32790 cm^{-1} . The band appearing at 28330 and 23810 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $^3T_1 (F) \rightarrow ^3T_1 (P)$ i.e. $d-d$ transition¹⁷. The band appearing at 32570 cm^{-1} and 29540 cm^{-1} may be

assigned to charge transfer transition. On the basis of magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectral data, it can be inferred that Ni^{II} complexes possess tetrahedral geometry. Mehta and Joishar¹⁹ have interpreted such observations in favour of tetrahedral Ni^{II} complexes.

The literature survey shows that palladium(II) complexes exhibit square planar geometry. The electronic spectrum of Pd^{II} complex display bands at 22600-23419, 27777-28500 and 29411-30300 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ ²⁰ transitions. Hence, a square planar geometry may be assigned to Pd^{II} complex. It is in fairly good agreement with the transitions suggested for Pd^{II} complexes having square planar environment of ligands²¹. This is further supported by diamagnetic behaviour of Pd^{II} complexes.

The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands and metal complexes were recorded in DMSO solvent. The ^1H NMR assignments are detailed in Table 3. It is important to emphasize that the ^1H resonances of the O-H groups at 10.20-11.57 ppm and 11.39-11.99 ppm for the ligands L_1 are similar for L_2 . The ^1H NMR signal observed for one of the -OH in the spectra of the ligands disappeared in the corresponding spectra of metal complexes confirming coordination to the central metal atom²².

The single proton resonances for CH=N group of these ligands occur at 8.32 ppm (Fig. 1) and 8.56 ppm for L₁ and L₂ respectively²³. The shift of this peak in the spectra of the metal complexes indicates coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the central metal atom. The aromatic ring resonances are observed at 6.78–7.88 ppm and 6.29–7.95 ppm as multiplets for ligands and metal complexes²⁴. The detailed ¹H NMR spectral data of the ligands are given in Table 3.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectra L₁.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectra of Co(L₁)₂·H₂O.

The thermal behaviour of the metal complexes was studied (Figs. 3 and 4). In case of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes TGA curve shows the weight loss around 80–100 °C indicating loss of water of crystallization. In case of Pd^{II} complexes the weight loss around 130 °C is attributed to the loss of coordinated water molecule. It can be

Fig. 3. Thermogravimetric curves of complexes of L₁.

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric curves of complexes of L₂.

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction curve of Ni(L₁)₂·H₂O.

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction curve of PdL₂·Cl·H₂O.

seen that for all the complexes decomposition begins around 250–300 °C and are completed around 650–850 °C. In TGA organic matter is decomposed after the loss of water molecules. After decomposition metal oxide remains as residue. The percentage weight loss at decomposition temperature is in agreement with the calculated values²⁵.

During X-ray powder diffraction of the complexes, major reflexes were measured and corresponding *d*-values were obtained using Bragg's equation. The independent indexing of major reflexes was carried out using

Table 4. Crystal lattice parameters of metal complexes

Complex	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>b</i> (Å)	<i>c</i> (Å)	<i>D</i> _{obs} (g/cm ³)	<i>D</i> _{cal} (g/cm ³)	Vol. (Å ³)	SD (%)	Porosity (%)
Co(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	31.10838 ±0.04117	21.22590 ±0.06116	21.06830 ±0.05074	1.5246	1.3306	13911.47	0.88	12.72
Ni(L ₁) ₂ .H ₂ O	31.08195 ±0.05526	19.29025 ±0.07351	21.13896 ±0.10114	1.6814	1.2294	12674.47	1.03	26.88
Pd(L ₁).Cl.H ₂ O	31.04263 ±0.04023	21.31858 ±0.05071	21.09852 ±0.04939	1.0708	0.7892	13962.68	0.70	26.29
Co(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	31.04788 ±0.08437	19.28934 ±0.06851	21.72304 ±0.09096	1.6854	1.3758	13009.78	1.27	18.39
Ni(L ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O	31.18076 ±0.08342	19.18754 ±0.11039	21.66972 ±0.13321	1.6514	1.3933	12964.60	1.52	18.65
Pd(L ₂).Cl.H ₂ O	31.26574 ±0.05615	19.16963 ±0.06405	21.62965 ±0.05483	1.1676	0.9207	12963.79	0.97	21.11

least square method. The miller indices *h*, *k*, *l* were calculated and refined by using Back-cal program on computer. The complexes were successfully indexed to orthorhombic crystal system with *Z* = 16 for all the complexes²⁶. Similar observations were reported in the literature. The lattice parameters are summarized in Table 4. The correctness of *d*-values was confirmed by comparing the observed density with that calculated from the X-ray diffractogram.

Based on spectroscopic investigations, the proposed structures of the metal complexes have been illustrated in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

where M = Co, Ni

Fig. 6. Structure of cobalt and nickel complexes of L₁.

where M = Co, Ni

Fig. 7. Structure of cobalt and nickel complexes of L₂.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade purchased from S. D. Fine chemicals (Mumbai) and were used without further purification.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

Schiff base was synthesized by general method^{7,8}. The amine, 4-hydroxybenzhydrazide (1.371 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in 20 ml ethanol and added to an ethanolic (20 ml) solution of each 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.221 g, 0.01 mol) and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (1.567 g, 0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio. The resulting solutions were refluxed for 3–4 h. The solution was reduced to ¼th of its original volume and poured in ice cold water. The solid precipitated were filtered off, washed with methanol and then recrystallized from ethanol. The purity of ligands was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis. The yield of the ligands was about 70–95%.

Synthesis of the complexes :

All the Schiff base complexes were prepared by adding stoichiometric amount of ligands to metal chlorides in a 2 : 1 or 1 : 1 mole ratio. To an ethanolic solution of 0.002 mol of Schiff base, ethanolic solution of metal chloride such as CoCl₂.6H₂O (0.001 mol), NiCl₂.6H₂O (0.001 mol), PdCl₂ (0.002 mol) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 4–5 h. The pH was adjusted to optimum level. The complexes which precipitated were filtered off, washed with cold methanol and recrystallized from ethanol. The products were finally dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

Metal content was determined in the laboratory by the reported methods⁹. C, H and N analyses were performed at the IIT, Mumbai. The infra-red spectra of the ligands and of their metal complexes were recorded in KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ region using a FTIR spectrum one supplied by Perkin-Elmer instrument. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO solution using a UV-Visible 2100 spectrophotometer supplied by M/s Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 25. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO using a Bruker Advance 300 MHz spectrometer. TGA was carried out using a Pyris Diamond TG-DTA supplied by Perkin-Elmer instruments. The X-ray analysis was carried out at TIFR, Mumbai.

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